

Co-creating in the third space with friends

A short interactive experience

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Boundary crossing, blended professionals working in the third space are “not constrained by structures and systems but rather cultivate strong relationships, interests and knowledge bases...” (McIntosh & Nutt, 2022). Rewarding third space participation is inherently relational and collaborative, beyond individual experiences: the activities in our three Slowposium live events invited participants to consider what impacts friendships and work alliances have on identity, collaboration and shared understandings of success in the third space.

In a liminal, interactive space, Steph and Jane, who are friends, colleagues and co-designers, invited participants to share and explore the themes of third space work where there are existing relationships between work roles.

- Are the boundaries less “boundy” when trust and commitment are already in place?
- Can existing relationships improve the outcomes of the work that occurs in the third space because values and goals are already formed?

In Mural, 3SS participants explored, in a welcoming, reflexive and conversational space, how relationships and friends impact co-design, success and outcomes in the third space. Together we considered the power of existing relationships and collegial networks in the success or otherwise of our work, celebrating the diversity of skills, qualifications and lived experience of third space practitioners.

Reference

McIntosh, E., & Nutt, D. (2022, May 18). Blended professionals: How to make the most of ‘third space’ experts. *Times Higher Education Campus Learn, Share, Connect*.
<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/blended-professionals-how-make-most-third-space-experts>

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